

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

Work Package WP4

Design of Mechanical Structure and Analysis

Deliverable D4.3

Detailed design

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO2 emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Deliverable details

This document provides a reference jacket, tower, and foundations for the X-Rotor wind turbine. Components such as shaft and bearing are also contemplated, as well as the cross-arm that serves as the connection between the blades and the tower. The verification of the provided structures with respect to internationally accepted design standards are provided

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1 Introduction

This report presents a detailed final design for the support structure for the 2-bladed X-Rotor wind turbine concept, a hybrid between a vertical and a horizontal axis wind turbine. To serve as a reference structure, standard concepts of a tower and a jacket were defined so that a comparison with the regular horizontal axis wind turbines is possible.

1.1 Load Analysis

The lumped operational load cases from the design basis, Silva (2021), were updated to include the wind speeds until the cut-off wind speed of 25m/s. Table 1 brings the mean wind speeds for a 10min sea state measure at 10m, U_{inf} , for the adopted bins and the correspondent mean significant wave heights, H_s , period, T_p , and probability of occurrence, p , defined from the joint probabilities distributions described in Silva (2021). The lower blade is fixed at 0 deg pitch, while the upper blade can pitch with an angle of θ_{upper} . The currently adopted design strategy makes use of negative pitch angles for wind speeds above rated wind speeds during operation. The load cases representing extreme event wind and wave condition with a return period of 50 years are shown in

Table 2, where the rotor is parked and the θ_{upper} covers a range of pitch angles the upper blade could be locked.

Table 1 Lumped operational load cases.

Load case ID	U_{inf} [m/s]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	p [-]	ω [RPM]	θ_{upper} [deg]
LC1	< 3.5	-	-	0.10987	-	-
LC2	4	0.9	7.6	0.07745	2.5	2
LC3	5	1.1	7.4	0.09304	3.2	2
LC4	6	1.3	7.3	0.10274	3.8	2
LC5	7	1.5	7.3	0.10582	4.5	2
LC6	8	1.7	7.3	0.10249	5.1	2
LC7	9	2.0	7.3	0.09380	5.7	2
LC8	10	2.2	7.3	0.08136	6.4	2
LC9	11	2.5	7.3	0.06702	7.0	2
LC10	12	2.7	7.4	0.05249	7.6	2
LC11	13	3.0	7.5	0.03910	8.0	-9.8
LC12	14	3.3	7.6	0.02772	8.0	-14.2
LC13	15	3.6	7.7	0.01871	8.0	-14.6
LC14	16	3.9	7.8	0.01202	8.0	-15.0
LC15	17	4.2	8.0	0.00735	8.0	-15.6
LC16	18	4.6	8.1	0.00427	8.0	-16.2
LC17	19	4.9	8.3	0.00236	8.0	-16.9
LC18	20	5.2	8.5	0.00124	8.0	-17.6
LC19	21	5.6	8.6	0.00062	8.0	-18.4
LC20	22	6.0	8.8	0.00030	8.0	-19.1
LC21	23	6.3	9.0	0.00013	8.0	-19.8
LC22	24	6.7	9.2	0.00006	8.0	-20.8
LC23	> 25.0	-	-	0.00002	8.0	-21.1

Table 2 – Extreme load cases

Load case ID	U_{inf} [m/s]	H_s [m]	T_p [s]	θ_{upper} [deg]
LC24	36.8	10.1	14.1	0
LC25	36.8	10.1	14.1	45
LC26	36.8	10.1	14.1	-45
LC27	36.8	10.1	14.1	90
LC28	36.8	10.1	14.1	-90

Aerodynamic loads

The resulting mean aerodynamic loads for a 2-bladed primary rotor were provided by Ajay (2022) for 45 points over one azimuthal rotation in terms of normal, F_N , and tangential forces, F_T , as well as pitching moment per blade unit length.

These components were combined and the resultant aerodynamic loads components at the tower top obtained. The coordinate system used is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Locals coordinate systems. (a) Plan view of rotor azimuthal angle, ϕ , and rotor angular speed, ω – Adapted from Paraschivoiu (2002). (b) Wind orientation of 0 degrees with respect to jacket coordinate system.

Here, only the resultant components from the normal force were adopted under the assumption that the secondary rotors thrust balance the remaining components. The aerodynamic load components for the operational load cases are shown on Figure 2 and Figure 3 exemplifies an extreme case were the upper blade it locked at 0 deg.

Figure 2 – Operational Aerodynamical Loads at the tower top. Adapted from Ajay (2022)

Figure 3 – Extreme aerodynamic loads for $U_{50} = 36.5$ m/s when upper blades are in flag position ($\theta = 0$ deg).

The extreme values for each component are shown in Table 3 for the operational loads cases defined and in Table 4 for the extreme load cases.

Table 3 – Extreme values of aerodynamic load components at tower top

Load case ID	F_z [MN]		F_x [MN]		F_y [MN]		M_z [MNm]		M_x [MNm]		M_y [MNm]	
	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max
LC1	0.00	0.14	-0.09	0.07	0.00	0.00	-1.69	1.92	0.00	3.21	1.23	0.11
LC2	0.00	0.19	-0.12	0.09	0.01	0.02	-1.56	3.19	-0.03	4.35	1.69	0.04
LC3	0.00	0.30	-0.19	0.14	0.02	0.04	-2.44	4.98	-0.04	6.79	2.65	0.07
LC4	0.00	0.43	-0.27	0.20	0.02	0.05	-3.52	7.17	-0.06	9.78	3.81	0.10
LC5	0.00	0.58	-0.37	0.27	0.03	0.07	-4.79	9.76	-0.08	13.31	5.19	0.13
LC6	0.00	0.76	-0.49	0.35	0.04	0.09	-6.25	12.75	-0.10	17.38	6.78	0.17
LC7	0.00	0.96	-0.62	0.44	0.05	0.12	-7.91	16.13	-0.13	22.00	8.58	0.22
LC8	0.00	1.18	-0.76	0.55	0.07	0.15	-9.77	19.92	-0.16	27.16	10.59	0.27
LC9	0.00	1.43	-0.92	0.66	0.08	0.18	-11.82	24.10	-0.19	32.86	12.82	0.32
LC10	0.00	1.70	-1.09	0.79	0.10	0.21	-14.06	28.68	-0.23	39.11	15.25	0.38
LC11	-0.13	1.91	-0.78	1.61	-0.97	-0.84	-76.18	7.33	-17.00	53.31	13.21	4.36
LC12	-0.25	2.03	-0.60	2.01	-1.31	-1.12	-110.13	2.15	-40.09	60.64	15.10	2.13
LC13	-0.28	2.11	-0.53	2.19	-1.34	-1.01	-120.88	0.28	-56.94	64.65	17.78	1.14
LC14	-0.32	2.11	-0.55	2.36	-1.37	-0.89	-131.41	0.14	-70.22	67.14	18.62	-0.66
LC15	-0.37	2.07	-0.58	2.54	-1.43	-0.80	-143.34	0.53	-78.29	66.30	17.71	-2.73
LC16	-0.43	2.17	-0.61	2.71	-1.49	-0.74	-155.93	1.07	-85.87	64.24	18.90	-4.43
LC17	-0.49	2.27	-0.64	2.88	-1.56	-0.69	-169.68	1.79	-94.94	59.85	20.77	-5.78
LC18	-0.55	2.38	-0.67	3.05	-1.63	-0.65	-188.03	2.24	-103.31	53.75	22.87	-7.24
LC19	-0.60	2.50	-0.69	3.20	-1.69	-0.61	-203.61	2.90	-112.78	51.33	25.17	-8.90
LC20	-0.65	2.63	-0.72	3.33	-1.75	-0.57	-220.15	3.38	-121.93	44.96	27.96	-10.55
LC21	-0.70	2.76	-0.74	3.42	-1.83	-0.54	-235.62	3.81	-131.39	43.30	31.06	-12.21
LC22	-0.74	2.89	-0.75	3.56	-1.94	-0.50	-249.17	4.21	-140.78	38.81	34.31	-14.04
LC23	-0.79	3.01	-0.78	3.68	-2.04	-0.47	-261.36	4.67	-148.48	38.73	37.32	-16.00

Table 4 - Extreme load cases

Load case ID	F_z [MN]		F_x [MN]		F_y [MN]		M_z [MNm]		M_x [MNm]		M_y [MNm]	
	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max	min	max
LC24	-1.49	2.72	-1.66	1.46	-0.22	0.23	-21.37	25.55	0.0	25.15	-2.16	18.99
LC25	-0.07	1.79	-1.65	0.55	-0.42	0.90	-4.05	98.65	-52.45	21.72	-13.81	27.46
LC26	-0.10	1.69	-0.59	1.57	-1.03	0.37	-108.54	4.21	-63.43	26.16	-17.00	38.92
LC27	0.0	1.09	-0.67	0.50	-0.47	0.47	-50.40	53.71	-95.81	0.0	-50.63	41.31
LC28	0.0	1.09	-0.66	0.51	-0.47	0.35	-51.41	52.85	-92.08	0.0	-48.35	36.25

The case when the wind speed is oriented diagonally to the jacket at 45 degrees was found to be more critical to the support structure. The wave direction was considered to be coaligned with the wind speed direction.

Figure 4 – Adopted coordinate system (a-b) Jacket.

2 Structural Model

The flexible multibody solver Fedem Windpower (v.7.2.1) was used to simulate the system composed by blades, cross-arm, tower, transition piece, jacket, and piles, Figure 5. The structure was modelled with beam elements based on the Euler-Bernoulli theory.

Figure 5 – Structural model in FEDEM Windpower.

A cylindrical tower connects the jacket transition piece to the base of the cross-arm that supports the blades. The transition piece connects the tower bottom to the top of the jacket, and it was considered as a rigid piece with the total weight of 473 tonnes maintained from the initial design Amiri (2021). The jacket stands on top of four individual piles.

2.1.1 Tower

A tower height of 55m was defined to maintain the secondary rotors on a height of circa 20m from the sea surface, as defined in Leithead (2019). The tower is segmented into four distinct sections, each characterized by its own cross-section profile. The upper-most section has a total length of 12m to match the size of the shaft allocated internally on that section. The subsequent sections' lengths were fixed as 15m, 14m and 14m. The weight of the shaft, bearings and rotary transformer, shown in Table 5, were distributed along their respective positions as point masses on the tower nodes.

Table 5 – Tower inner components' mass

Component	Mass [tonnes]
Shaft	371
Bearing 1	119
Bearing 2	42
Rotary transformer	4.2

2.1.2 Cross-arm

A cross arm with a total 50m length lay on the top of the tower and connects the shaft to the base of the blades, Figure 6, rotating with them and composing the primary rotor. To minimize the aerodynamic resistance, the cross arm is designed as a cylindrical section.

Figure 6 – Cross arm model.

2.1.3 Jacket

A four-legged-jacket was established as the support structure by Leithead (2019) to a reference site of 40m water depth, which requires a jacket height of 56.1 m. The UpWind jacket, Vorpahl (2013), was used as initial reference. Despite that it was designed for 50m water depth, it made use of the NREL 5MW baseline horizontal axis wind turbine that has a rated power slightly under the preliminary estimation for the X-Rotor wind turbine of 5.5MW. To compensate for the high overturning moments, shown in Table 3 and Table 3, the Upwind reference jacket's upper and lower widths were increased by a factor of 2.5 during the initial design assessment conducted by Amiri (2021), as it is shown Figure 7. The respective resulting values of 20m and 30m were used throughout this study in order to maintain the battle angle comparable to regular jackets such as the UpWind reference design, Vorpahl (2013).

Figure 7 – Upwind jacket (left) scaling to improve the overturning capacity of X-Rotor jacket (right). Source: Silva (2023).

To reduce the overall mass, the jacket was detailed with joint cans. This allows the cross-section independence between the leg and X-braces members and the leg joint chords and stubs. The joints are connected to the longer members by conical transitions. Two types of welded connections are then created. The first one, the welded connection between the joint stubs and joint chord; and the second one, the welded connection between the joint and the leg and X-braces longer members, formed by conical transitions. Figure 8 illustrates a typical joint and its connections.

Figure 8 – Illustrative joint connection with a cross section reduction of 0.8 on the long members with respect to the adjacent joint connection.

A material damping of 2% was adopted for the steel. For simplicity, the Rayleigh damping, c , was used and the proportional mass, α , and stiffness, β , components calculated based on the damping ratio, λ_i , and the first two natural frequencies, ω_1 and ω_2 (rad/s), considering a system with a rigid rotor as follows:

$$c = \alpha m + \beta k$$

$$\lambda_i = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\alpha}{\omega_i} + \beta \omega_i \right)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{2\omega_1\omega_2}{\omega_2^2 - \omega_1^2} (\lambda_1\omega_2 - \lambda_2\omega_1)$$

$$\beta = \frac{2(\omega_2\lambda_2 - \omega_1\lambda_1)}{\omega_2^2 - \omega_1^2}$$

The resulting mass proportional damping of $\alpha = 0.132$ and a stiffness proportional damping of $\beta = 0.00255$ were applied on the jacket, tower, cross-arm, and foundations along their design. At the moment this study

was made, the aerodynamic damping of the X-Rotor turbine was not completely understood. Thus, as a conservative assumption, no aerodynamic damping was adopted.

2.1.4 Blades

The blades' dimensions and detailed internal components defined in the initial design, Amiri (2021), were used as a reference to this model. The spanwise mass and stiffness were obtained through NREL PRECOMP for the pre-defined dimensions are shown in Figure 9. However, the blades were still considered to be rigid in this study and only the respective upper and lower blades mass distribution was included on the analysis.

Figure 9 – Blade Spanwise structural properties obtained by NREL PreComp.

The secondary rotors were included as a point masses, of 10 ton each, attached to the tip of the lower blades.

2.1.5 Foundations

The bottom of the jacket legs were considered to be rigidly connected to the piles by grouted connections. The piles were modelled as interconnected beams containing free joints with nonlinear springs to simulate the soil-pile interaction. These springs represent the values obtained for the lateral soil resistance and lateral displacement (p-y) curves, and axial pile transfer-displacement (t-z) curve, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – Pile structural model.

The upper most 10m of the piles were discretized with element of 1m length. From 10m to the pile end tip, elements with 10m length were adopted to improve the computational efficiency of the model without a bigger compromise of accuracy, once the larger displacements occur at the pile top.

2.1.6 Rotor

The mass distribution of the rotor components considered on the model is shown in Table 7 and illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11 - Structural members of the rotational part of X-rotor.

Table 6 - Mass distribution of the rotational part of the wind turbine

		Mass	X1	X2	Y1	Y2	c_x	c_y	M_x	M_y	d_y	I_x
		kg	m	m	m	m	m	m	kg · m	kg · m	m	kg · m ²
1	Cross-arm	583984	0	-25	0	25	0	0	0	0	0	121663409
2	Upper blade 1	40500	0	-25	87	-75	43	-50	1753650	-2025000	-50	109687500
3	Lower blade 1	23384	0	-25	-42	-75	-21	-50	-492233	-1169200	-50	63331667
4	Upper blade 1	40500	0	-25	87	75	43	50	1753650	2025000	50	109687500
5	Lower blade 2	23384	0	25	-42	75	-21	50	-492233	1169200	50	63331667
7	2rd rotor 1	10000	-42	-75	-42	-75	-42	-75	-421000	-750000	-	56250000
8	2rd rotor 2	10000	-42	75	-42	75	-42	75	-421000	750000	-	56250000
Total		731752	-	-	-	-	2	0	1680834	0	-	580201743

Where (X1, Y1) and (X2, Y2) are the local coordinates of the two ends of each structure, c_x and c_y are the mass centers of the structures in x and y dimension respectively, M_x and M_y are the moment of mass in x and y dimension respectively, d_y is the parallel axis, I_x is the moment of inertia in x dimension.

2.2 Design Methodology

2.2.1 Jacket

The stresses on the members are dependent both on the members loading and the geometry of the connections. Thus, a balance in between the member cross section and the stress concentration factor (SCF) of its connection is required.

To reduce the value of the stress concentration factors (SCFs), some of their geometrical ratios were fixed at values known to contribute to this reduction. In addition, fixing these ratios also facilitate the optimization of the jacket structure by reducing the number of variables.

In the case of the connections between the joint chord with the joint’s stubs, the Efthymiou formulation with thickness correction DNV-ST-C203 was adopted. These SCFs are dependent on the geometrical ratios described in the equations below, where D and T refer to the outer diameter and thickness of the joint chord, L to the joint chord length, and d and t to the outer diameter and thickness of the joint stubs.

$$\beta = \frac{d}{D} \quad \alpha = \frac{2L}{D} \quad \gamma = \frac{D}{2T} \quad \tau = \frac{t}{T}$$

As demonstrated in Figure 12, there is a decrease in the SCF for smaller values of γ . Thus, the lower limit value of 8 was adopted. Similarly, the α lower limit of 4 for the use of the Efthymiou equations was adopted.

Figure 12 – Sensibility of the axial component SCF on the chord and brace side of a Y Joint with respect to its ratios. Adapted from Lotsberg (2018).

The values of the reference Upwind jacket for β and τ were maintained as 0.6. Despite this value not being optimum in terms of the resultant SCFs, it ensures that the braces can provide enough stiffness to the jacket and contribute to load distribution, avoiding larger relative displacement between the legs.

After the geometrical ratios are fixed, T , d and t could be defined in terms of the leg chord diameter, D . The term 'diameter' used in this document refers specifically to the 'outer diameter' unless otherwise is stated. For the case of the conical transitions between joints and longer members, the SCF formulation for conical transitions from DNV-ST-C203, were adopted:

$$SCF = 1 + \frac{0.6t\sqrt{D_j(t_j + t_c)}}{t^2} \tan \alpha_c$$

for the tubular member side, and

$$SCF = 1 + \frac{0.6t\sqrt{D_j(t_j + t_c)}}{t_c^2} \tan \alpha_c$$

for the cone side, where D_j is the diameter of the connected member, t is this member's wall thickness, t_c the cone wall thickness, and α_c the slope angle of the conical transition.

The elements representing the conical transitions were not included in the model, but rather in the post-processing analysis. The loading from the node at the connection in between the joints and long members was used to assess the welded connections on both sides of the conical transition: the joint side and the longer member side. For this, a hypothetical conical member diameter was used as the average between the diameters of longer member and the connected member of the joint. The conical transition length, L_{cone} was limited to about 1m to reduce imprecisions of the simulation model.

It was assumed that the thickness transition was placed on the cone side and distributed over a length that respects the ratio of 4:1 from the difference between the thickness of the connected member and the cone. The cone thickness, t_c , was set as the average between the thickness of the two connected members, as this was shown to reduce the SCF of the conical transition.

As the equations above show, these SCFs are proportional to the slope angle of the conical transition, α_c . This slope can be reduced by increasing the conical transition length, L_{cone} , (here limited) or by reducing the difference between the diameters of the connected members. This presents a challenge, as although the reduction of the cross-section on the longer members is desired for the overall mass reduction, if done excessively, it results in a sudden increase of the SCFs besides the expected increase in the inner loading.

Figure 13 – Sensibility of the SCF of the conical transition on the cone side with respect to the parameters that influence the slope angle of the cone.

When referring to cross-section reduction, a decrease in the diameter of the longer member, d_{long} , with respect to the diameter of the connected joint member is denoted (d_{long}/D or d_{long}/d)

Once these geometrical ratios were fixed, all the members' cross-sections could be defined in terms of the diameter of chord of the leg joint. Each bay has independent parameters and could be sized independently. However, the leg chord diameter was set constant along the bays. The legs are highly loaded in the axial direction due to the large overturning moments produced by the aerodynamic loads and a geometrical change in their cross-section would generate a non-favourable increase in final stresses.

An increase of the leg chord diameter (the primary parameter) was performed until a satisfactory result was obtained. The cross-section reduction for both leg long members and X-braces long members were simultaneously adjusted so that a better utilization ratio could be achieved in different bays.

The sizing of the members was done with the support of the local approach described by Schafhirt (2016), where it was assumed that the loading on a node does not change during a small change of member cross-section. The strategy adopted here to fix the values of the SCFs is consistent with this assumption. This approach allows a more efficient sizing of elements, as less simulations are needed and are only done after an internal loop redefines a new cross-section candidate.

The jacket and tower were designed interactively. The cross-arm, bearings and shaft were designed in separate studies, and included in the support structure in a modular fashion.

To calculate the fatigue damage of the connections using the Palmgren-Miner rule, different S-N curves were used depending on the detailed component analysed. For the welded connections between the joint chord and joint stubs, the S-N curve for Tubular connections was adopted. For the conical transition, the F3 curve, while, in case of no reduction of cross section between joints and longer members, the SN curve F was adopted under the assumption that the weld is done on one side only with the use of a backing bar. The tower was analysed using the S-N curve C, while considering an automatic longitudinal seam weld of each of its sections.

It was assumed that during the design lifetime of 20 years, the jacket would not undergo inspection. Thus, the total fatigue damage of its members was multiplied by a design fatigue factor (DFF) of 3. As the tower can more easily be inspected, programmed inspections were considered and a DFF of 1 adopted.

2.2.2 Foundations

The pile design aimed to have the diameter of the piles, D_p , as small as possible to ease the driving process during installation. API 2A-WSD (2014) recommends a minimum pile wall thickness t_p of:

$$t_p(mm) = 6.35 + \frac{D_p(mm)}{100}.$$

The minimum diameter to thickness ratio $D_p/t_p > 40$ was respected, as recommended by API RP2GEO (2014).

Soil-piles reaction under lateral loads

The top pile displacement was limited to $0.1\%D_p$ to limit the soil stiffness degradation.

The lateral loads are resisted by bending moments of the piles as well as passive supports from the surrounding soil, which presents a soil-structure interaction problem. The soil resistance and the pile displacement depend on each other. The p-y curve, as introduced in Figure 10, describes the relationship between lateral soil resistance and lateral displacement, that can be calculated as:

$$p = Ap_u \tanh\left(\frac{kz}{Ap_u}\right)$$

where $A = 0.9$ for cyclic loading; k is the rate of increase with depth of initial modulus of subgrade reaction; y is the lateral deflection at depth z ; z is the depth below the original seafloor; p_u is the ultimate lateral resistance at depth z , which is taken as the smaller value of p_{us} and p_{ud} ($s = \text{shallow}$, $d = \text{deep}$).

$$p_{us} = (C_1 z + C_2 D_p) \gamma' z$$

$$p_{ud} = C_3 D_p \gamma' z$$

where γ' is the submerged soil unit weight; C_1 , C_2 , C_3 are the coefficients determined as function of the angle of friction of sand ϕ' as defined in Silva (2021).

$$C_1 = \frac{(\tan \beta)^2 \tan \alpha}{\tan(\beta - \phi')} + K_o \left[\frac{\tan \phi' \sin \beta}{\cos \alpha \tan(\beta - \phi')} + \tan \beta (\tan \phi' \sin \beta - \tan \alpha) \right]$$

$$C_2 = \frac{\tan \beta}{\tan(\beta - \phi')} - K_o$$

$$C_3 = K_o [(\tan \beta)^8 - 1] + K_o \tan \phi' (\tan \beta)^4$$

where $\alpha = \phi'/2$ and $\beta = 45 + \phi'/2$.

To control the material consumption and limit the cost of the pile design, piles with different thickness were proposed to be applied in different depths according to the stress level while the diameter of the pile was set constant to facilitate the construction process. Thus, in some locations, pile segments with different thicknesses will be connected with each other. Stresses in these transition sections are then increased due to the geometry change. In this situation, the nominal stresses are scaled with stress concentration factors (SCFs) to get more realistic stresses in the transition sections.

To verify the pile capacity and performance for ultimate limit state (ULS) analysis, load cases with power production condition and the parked condition were considered according to DNVGL-ST-0437, as shown in Table 7.

For the power production condition, the wind speed of 19m/s with conditional significant wave height of 4.3m and the mean of the conditional peak period of 8.0s were used. The aerodynamic loads for DLC 1.1 - 1.5 are calculated with the rotor rotating at designed rotational speed. For the parked condition we use the EWM wind speed of 36.8 m/s, ESS significant wave height of 10.1 m and peak period of 14.1 s (Li et al, 2015) and the aerodynamic loads for DLC 6.1 - 6.5 are calculated with the rotor in parked state.

Table 7 – Piles design load cases

Design situation	DLC	Wind	Wave	Wind and wave directionality
Power production	1.1	NTM	NSS	0°
	1.2	NTM	NSS	45°
	1.3	NTM	NSS	-45°
	1.4	NTM	NSS	90°
	1.5	NTM	NSS	-90°
Parked	6.1	EWM	ESS	0°
	6.2	EWM	ESS	45°
	6.3	EWM	ESS	-45°
	6.4	EWM	ESS	90°
	6.5	EWM	ESS	-90°

NTM: normal turbulence model

NSS: normal sea state, joint prob. Distribution

EWM: extreme wind speed model (50-year)

ESS: extreme sea state (50-year)

Ultimate axial pile capacity

The pile ultimate axial capacity is evaluated according to API RP2GEO (2014), which includes the shaft friction capacity and the end bearing capacity. The pile capacity is evaluated based on an ideal assumption of a (quasi-) static and monotonic application of the axial loads and has no reflection on the dynamic interaction between pile and soil during field conditions, as shown in the equation below:

$$Q_c = Q_{f,c} + Q_p = f(z)A_s + qA_p,$$

where Q_c is the ultimate axial capacity of the piles in compression; $Q_{f,c}$ is the shaft friction capacity in compression, in force units; Q_p is the end bearing capacity, in force units, $f(z)$ is the unit shaft friction, in stress units; A_s is the side surface area of the pile; q is the unit end bearing at the pile tip, in stress units; A_p is the gross end area of the pile; and z is the depth below the original seafloor.

The maximum and minimum loads obtained on the pile head were obtained by the time domain response of the jacket without piles with clamped bottom connections. These values are summarized Table 8, where the negative values represent the pullout loads.

Figure 14 – Pile ID

Table 8 – Extreme vertical loads at the lower end of the fixed-based jacket legs.

DLC	Max F_x [kN]	Leg	Min F_x [kN]	leg
1.1	17419.85	2	-3638.15	4
1.2	17232.77	2	-3397.35	4
1.3	17352.77	2	-3625.80	4
1.4	16992.68	2	-3210.28	4
1.5	17419.85	2	-1759.31	1
6.1	12042.52	3	641.94	1
6.2	11956.94	4	692.96	2
6.3	11406.04	1	714.96	3
6.4	13717.48	2	-744.58	4
6.5	11108.65	2	1767.79	1

The power production DLCs cause higher axial loads than the parked DLCs for both compression and tension loads, which means that the cyclic aerodynamic loads from the rotating rotor are more critical for the pile design than the static loads from more extreme wind and wave conditions. The most critical loads as shown in bold font are considered for the pile capacity design, with a ULS safety factor of 1.25.

FLS analysis

The fatigue limit state analysis of the piles was based on DNV-ST-C203 and Oest (2017).

The local coordinate system of the pile sections is set so that the x-axis points downward along the pile segments and the y- and z-axis are normal to the pile segments. The stresses around the pile cross-sections are calculated in 8 sample points represented by the angle α_{si} , defined starting from the positive direction of y-axis and numbered clockwise. To calculate the hot spot stresses, first the principal stresses σ_{x_i} , σ_{y_i} and σ_{z_i} are calculated from the FEDEM loading analysis of forces and moment, F_x , F_y , F_z , M_x , M_y , M_z .

To be conservative, only the maximum stresses on the outer surface of the piles are evaluated.

$$\sigma_{x_i} = SCF \left(\frac{F_x}{A_s} - \frac{M_y D_s I_s \sin \alpha_{si}}{2} - \frac{M_z D_s I_s \cos \alpha_{si}}{2} \right)$$

$$\sigma_{Y_i} = \frac{F_y}{A_s} - \frac{M_x D_s J_s \sin \alpha_{si}}{2}$$

$$\sigma_{Z_i} = \frac{F_z}{A_s} - \frac{M_x D_s J_s \cos \alpha_{si}}{2}$$

Here A_s is the section area, I_s is the bending moment of inertia and J_s is the polar moment of inertia of the section.

The SCF due to the eccentricities caused by the thickness difference in between different cross-sections recommended by DNV-ST-C203 is used:

$$SCF = 1 - \frac{6(\delta_t - \delta_m)}{t_1} \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{T_1}{t_1}\right)^\beta} e^{-\alpha}$$

where:

$$\alpha = \frac{1.82L}{\sqrt{D_s t_1}} \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{T_1}{t_1}\right)^\beta}$$

$$\beta = 1.5 - \frac{1.0}{\log\left(\frac{D_s}{t_1}\right)} + \left[\frac{3.0}{\log\left(\frac{D_s}{t_1}\right)} \right]^2$$

Here L is the length of the slope, T_1 is the thickness of the thicker end and t_1 is the thickness of the thinner end of the pile, $\delta_m = 0$ is the misalignment from the inner side of the pile shaft, and $\delta_t - \delta_m$ is the misalignment from the neutral axis.

In the fatigue check, the stress used for analysis depends on the material's fatigue behaviour and the type of loading the component experiences. The Von Mises stress is an equivalent stress used for complex loading scenarios, which is especially useful in multi-axial fatigue analysis, as it considers the combined effect of different stress components, providing a more accurate representation of the fatigue behaviour for complex loading conditions. The Von-Mises stresses are obtained according to the principal stresses as:

$$\sigma_{V_i} = \sqrt{\frac{(\sigma_{X_i} - \sigma_{Y_i})^2 + (\sigma_{Y_i} - \sigma_{Z_i})^2 + (\sigma_{Z_i} - \sigma_{X_i})^2}{2}}$$

For the piles, the SN-curve E was adopted with a condition that the tubular girth welds were to be made from the outside. Furthermore, the S-N curve for the air environment condition was used for the pile driving phase, under the assumption that no corrosion is expected on the pile during the installation. The S-N curve for seawater with cathodic protection was used for the operational life.

2.2.3 Cross-arm

The cross-arm is formed by a tapered cross-section composed by a larger diameter at the center that is reduced until the end extremities attach to the blades. Displacements and deformation due to the bending moments and centrifugal forces are considered as the focus of the cross-arm design.

The bending moments acting on the cross-arm are a result from its self-weight, weight of the primary rotor, secondary rotors and generators, and aerodynamic loads. Due to the bending moments, the largest displacement of the cross-arm occurs at the two ends that connects to the blades. To limit the amplitude of the displacement and deformation, the sections should have sufficient bending stiffness. Two types of sections, as shown in Figure 15, were compared, where section A is a hollow cylinder, and section B is hollow

cylinder enhanced by an inner plate that acts as a stiffener. For the convince of the analysis, the plate has the same thickness of the cylinder wall. The comparison intended to find the section with larger bending stiffness for the same mass.

Figure 15 - Two types of sections of the cross-arm for comparison of the bending stiffness. Section A is a hollow cylinder, and Section B is a hollow cylinder enhanced by a plate with the same thickness of the cylinder’s shell.

The relationship of bending stiffness and diameter and mass of the two sections are shown in Figure 16. For the same amount of material consumption, the hollow cylinder with larger diameter shows a higher bending stiffness than a smaller cylinder with an inner stiffener. Thus, the hollow cylinder without an inner stiffener is chosen for the cross-arm design.

Figure 16 - The bending stiffness (left axis) and diameter (right axis) change with mass, Section A is a pure cylinder, Section B is a cylinder enhanced by a plate with the same thickness of the cylinder, the thickness of all structural elements is taken as 3cm.

The next consideration is the deformation of the cross-arm due to the centrifugal forces. As is illustrated in Figure 17, the centrifugal forces are from the cross-arm’s own inertial force, F , and the external centrifugal force F_b from the primary rotor, secondary rotors, and generators during rotation. The resultant length of the cross-arm, considering the additional strain due to the centrifugal forces, are described in the equation below:

$$L = \frac{3E - \sqrt{9E^2 - 12\rho\omega^2L_0^2(C + E)}}{2\rho\omega^2L_0}$$

where L_0 is the length of the cross-arm without rotation, ω is the rotational speed in rad/s, $C = F_b/A$ represents the external force, and A is the area of the cross-arm section. In this equation, a constant section area along the cross-arm is assumed.

The stretched length of the arm is defined as $\Delta = L - L_0$. The relationship of Δ and the unit length mass is shown in Figure 17, where $L_0 = 25\text{ m}$ is the half length of the cross-arm, $\omega = 0.83\text{ rad/s}$ is the rated rotational speed. The length Δ is calculated from the hub center to one end of the arm.

Figure 17 - The stretched length Δ (left axis) and diameter (right axis) change with mass, three different thicknesses $t=10\text{mm}$, 15mm and 30 mm are compared.

The presence of the cross-arm introduced an additional aerodynamic drag to the system, which results in a power loss. The aerodynamic drag force can be expressed as:

$$F_d = \frac{C_d \rho u^2 A_r}{2}$$

where C_d is the drag coefficient; ρ is the mass density of air; u is the flow speed of the cylinder relative to the fluid; $A_r = D_o L$ is the reference area; and D_o is the outer diameter.

The value of C_d of the cross-arm depends on the Reynolds number Re , which is given by:

$$Re = \frac{\rho u D}{\mu}$$

where $D = D_o$ is the characteristic diameter and μ is dynamic fluid viscosity. The mean values and envelop of Re along the cross-arm are shown in the Figure 18:

Figure 18 - The maximum, mean and minimum value of Reynolds number along the cross-arm.

The torque Q_d from the drag force F_d is calculated by:

$$Q_d = \int_0^L F_d dl$$

The values of Q_d with azimuth angle and wind speed are shown in Figure 19:

Figure 19 - The torque with azimuth angle and wind speed.

The power loss due to the aerodynamic drag on the cross-arm is estimated by the equation below:

$$P_d = \sum_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sum_{-L}^L F_d u$$

The result of the power loss is shown in Figure 20.

Figure 20 - The power loss due to aerodynamic drag on the cross arm.

For the FLS analysis of the main cross-arm cross section, the S-N curve B1 was adopted, with the condition that the section was non-welded.

2.2.4 Shaft

The shaft is designed with two different cylindrical cross-sections connected by a transition piece to reduce the total required mass. A larger diameter on the upper part accommodates the Bearing 1, and a smaller diameter on the lower part accommodates the Bearing 2. This is illustrated in Figure 21, as well as the sections distributions and bearing reference.

Figure 21 - Shaft design illustration and sections for FLS check.

The shaft needs to accommodate the mass of the rotor, which is detailed in Table 6 for the components illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 22 illustrates the reference frame of the loads on top of the shaft-bearing system, and Table 9, the forces (F_X , F_Y and F_Z) and moments (M_X , M_Y and M_Z) applied to the ULS design of the shaft. The maximum dynamic forces are taken because they were found to be larger than the extreme static forces. F_H is the resultant force of F_Y and F_Z , and M_H is the resultant moment of M_Y and M_Z , which represent the maximum levels of forces and moments on the shaft.

Table 9 – ULS shaft design loads

Load component	Max dynamic loading on top of shaft
F_X [MN]	5.64
F_Y [MN]	0.398
F_Z [MN]	-5.03
M_X (shaft) [MNm]	-5.03
M_X [MNm]	395
M_Y [MNm]	-7.75
F_H [MN]	5.04
M_H [MNm]	396

Figure 22 - Design load on top of the shaft for ULS design

A major function of the shaft is to carry the torque safely. The torque comes from three sources: the aerodynamic and inertial moment from normal operation, the aerodynamic moment from failure mode of the secondary rotors and the inertial moment from braking. To be conservative, the torque for the shaft design considers the moments in three directions. When the value of the torque is obtained, the section size of the shaft can be initially determined. In this step, the design process in Clarke et al. (2014) is taken as a reference.

First, an ultra-high strength steel AISI 4340 is chosen to be applied to the main shaft of X-rotor wind turbine. AISI 4340 is known as a medium-carbon, low-alloy steel that has high toughness and strength in the heat-treated condition. The yield strength σ_y of AISI 4340 is:

$$\sigma_y = 420.51 \text{ MPa}$$

Since the maximum principal stress is σ_y and the minimum principal stress is zero, from the maximum shear stress theory:

$$\tau_{max1} = \frac{\sigma_y}{2} = 210.25 \text{ MPa}$$

The torsion formula for a solid cylindrical shaft is:

$$\tau_s = \frac{TD_0}{2J}$$

Here the polar moment of inertia is

$$J = \frac{\pi}{2} \left[\left(\frac{D_0}{2} \right)^4 - \left(\frac{D_i}{2} \right)^4 \right]$$

T is the torque on the shaft, D_0 is outer diameter (m) and D_i is inner diameter (m).

According to the parameters introduced above, the section size of the shaft can be initially determined so that the shaft is able to survive with the maximum shear stress τ_{max} of the material.

In order to make a safe design, a failure state of the two secondary rotors is considered, i.e., it is assumed that there is no thrust output from the secondary rotors and all the aerodynamic torque M_a generated from the primary rotor is assumed to be carried by the shaft. Thus, the torque M from rotor rotation is taken as:

$$M = M_x + M_a = -5.03 \times 10^6 - 6.07 \times 10^7 \text{ Nm}$$

where the negative sign marks the direction of the moment. Moreover, the wind turbine inertia moment from the process of braking should also be considered. During the braking process of the wind turbine, the rotational speed of the rotor is assumed to be reduced from rated rotational speed Ω to zero with a constant angular acceleration α . The breaking time initially adopted for the ULS design was $t = 20s$. This value was later re-evaluated for the FLS.

$$\Omega = 7.96 \text{ RPM}$$

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi\Omega}{60t}$$

Thus:

$$\alpha = 0.042 \text{ rad} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$$

Thus, the structure inertia torque due to the emergency brake is obtained as:

$$T_{total} = M + T = 9.00 \times 10^7 \text{ Nm}$$

Based on these parameters, a dimension of the shaft section is estimated as: $D_0 = 1.6m$, $D_i = 1.1m$. These values are comparable with the dimensions of the main shaft of a 5MW horizontal axis wind turbine with $D_0 = 1.75m$, $D_i = 1.25m$ as introduced in Nejad et al. (2016). The usage factor for the ULS design is:

$$\eta_{ULS} = \frac{\tau_s}{\tau_{max1}} = 0.69 < 1.0$$

Shaft FLS analysis

There are two targets to be accomplished in this step:

- Check the fatigue life of the shaft to satisfy the 20 years of operating time.
- Optimize the design to minimize the weight of the shaft.

Shaft FLS design method

To perform fatigue analysis, two sets of data are required: stress time history and S-N curves. The cyclic stress is represented by Von Mises stresses on the outer surface of each shaft section. The S-N curve represents the relationship between the applied stress amplitude, $\Delta\sigma$, and the number of cycles to failure, N , for a given material. The S-N curves for base material of the shaft and butt weld for the section transition are taken from DNV-ST-C203 as:

- S-N curves for base material of high strength steel is applied to other sections without butt weld:

$$\log N = 17.446 - 4.70 \log \Delta\sigma$$

- C1 in air is applied to the butt weld with the condition that it is a circumferential butt weld made from both sides dressed flush:

$$\log N = \text{Min}(12.449 - 3.0 \log \Delta\sigma, 16.081 - 5.0 \log \Delta\sigma)$$

The cumulative damage is calculated according to the operating load cases and their probability as is described in Table 1. The fatigue damage factor f_d is

$$f_d = \sum_{j=1}^m P_j \sum_{i=1}^{k_m} \frac{n_i}{N_i}$$

where m is the number of load cases, k_m is the number of load levels in each load case, P_j is the probability of the occurrence of each load case, n_i is the number of applied loading cycles corresponding to the i th load level, and N_i is the number of cycles to failure at the i th load level.

From load analysis it was found that the stresses reduce significantly from the top of the shaft to the lower end of the shaft. This analysis makes it possible to reduce the total mass of the shaft by using a smaller-diameter cylinder at the lower end of the shaft. To avoid stress concentration from inside and simplify the construction process, the strategy of the optimization was to keep the inner diameter constant all along the shaft and narrow down the outer diameter (with slope of 1:4), as is shown in Figure 23, while the fatigue life is satisfied. T_1 is the thickness of the larger end and t_1 is the thickness of the smaller end, L is the length of the slope and δ_t is the eccentricity of the thickness.

Figure 23 Stress concentration due to shaft section transition, adapted from DNV (2014).

According to Lotsberg (1998), the stress concentration factors, SCF , for the transition section is given as:

$$SCF = 1 + \frac{6(\delta_t + \delta_m + \delta_0)}{t_1} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{T_1}{t_1}\right)^\beta}$$

where:

$$\alpha 1 = \frac{1.82L}{\sqrt{Dt_1}} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{T_1}{t_1}\right)^{\beta 1}}$$

$$\beta 1 = 1.5 - \frac{1.0}{\log\left(\frac{D}{t_1}\right)} + \left[\frac{3.0}{\log\left(\frac{D}{t_1}\right)} \right]^2$$

D is the diameter at of the larger section, $\delta_m = 0$ is the misalignment from the inner side of the shaft, and δ_0 is the eccentricity inherent in the S-N curve, which is taken as $0.1t_1$ as recommended by DNV-ST-C203.

2.2.5 Bearings

There are two bearings that support the shaft. The first one is a tapered bearing and the second one is a roller bearing, as illustrated in Figure 24.

Figure 24 – General bearing and breaking layout.

The parameters that need to be determined in this design are shown in Figure 25 and Figure 26. The highlighted parameters will be analyzed for the design.

Figure 25 - Design parameters for tapered roller bearing, outer ring outside diameter (D), outer ring inside diameter (E), inner ring guide flange diameter (d_{Si}), inner bore diameter (d), pitch circle diameter (D_{pw}), width (B), width of outer ring (B_e), width of inner ring (B_i), effective roller length (L_{we}), nominal roller diameter (D_w), nominal contact angle (α), the distance between center of bearing and center of roller (δ_{CR}).

Figure 26 - Design parameters for cylindrical roller bearing, outer ring outside diameter (D), outer ring inside diameter (d_e), outer ring guide flange diameter (d_{Se}), inner ring guide flange diameter (d_{Si}), inner ring inside diameter (d_i), inner bore diameter (d), pitch circle diameter (D_{pw}), width (B), effective roller length (L_{we}), nominal roller diameter (D_w).

Bearing design rules and regulations

- Static load ratings

The basic static radial load rating for radial roller bearings is defined by ISO 76 (2006-05-01) as:

$$C_{0r} = 44 \left(1 - \frac{D_w \cos \alpha}{D_{p\omega}} \right) i Z L_{\omega e} D_w \cos \alpha$$

where i is the number of rows of rolling elements, and Z is the number of rolling elements in a single row bearing. The basic static axial load rating for thrust roller bearings is defined by ISO 76 (2006-05-01) as:

$$C_{0a} = 220 \left(1 - \frac{D_{\omega} \cos \alpha}{D_{p\omega}} \right) Z L_{\omega e} D_{\omega} \sin \alpha$$

The static equivalent axial load for the thrust roller bearings with $\alpha \neq 90^\circ$ is given by the equation:

$$P_{0a} = 2.3F_r \tan \alpha + F_a$$

Here F_r is the radial component of actual bearing load, and F_a is the axial component of actual bearing load.

The static safety factors in both directions are defined as:

$$S_{0r} = \frac{C_{0r}}{P_{0r}}$$

The guideline value of S_{0r} is 3 for roller bearings running with load fluctuation.

- Dynamic load ratings

The basic dynamic radial load rating for a radial roller bearing is given by ISO 281 (2007-02-15) as:

$$C_r = b_m f_c (i L_{\omega e} \cos \alpha)^{\frac{7}{9}} Z^{\frac{3}{4}} D_{\omega}^{\frac{29}{27}} \cos \alpha$$

Dynamic equivalent radial load for single bearings is defined as:

$$P_r = X F_r + Y F_a$$

where X is dynamic radial load factor and Y is dynamic axial load factor. The basic rating life (in million revolutions) for a radial roller bearing is given by the life equation:

$$L_{10} = \left(\frac{C_r}{P_r} \right)^{\frac{10}{3}}$$

In this International Standard, a life modification factor, a_{ISO} , is introduced, based on a systems approach of life calculation in addition to the modification factor a_1 ,

$$a_{ISO} = f \left(\frac{e_c C_u}{P}, \kappa \right)$$

where e_c is contamination factor, which evaluates the life reduction due to the contamination in the lubricant film in the race way. The value of e_c depends on the level of contamination: from 0, for very severe contamination, to 1, for extreme cleanliness, according to ISO 281 (2007-02-15). Here $e_c = 0.7$ is taken for the normal cleanliness case. C_u is the fatigue load limit, which is calculated based on a simplified method as

$$C_u = \frac{C_r}{8.2} \left(\frac{100}{D_{p\omega}} \right)^{0.3} \quad \text{for } D_{p\omega} > 100 \text{ mm}$$

$\kappa = 1.6$ is viscosity ratio.

According to the parameters described above, the life modification factor a_{ISO} is estimated as follows:

For radial roller bearings:

$$a_{ISO} = 0.1 \left[1 - \left(1.5859 - \frac{1.2348}{\kappa^{0.071739}} \right) \left(\frac{e_C C_u}{P} \right)^{0.4} \right]^{-9.185} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq \kappa \leq 4$$

For thrust roller bearings:

$$a_{ISO} = 0.1 \left[1 - \left(1.5859 - \frac{1.2348}{\kappa^{0.071739}} \right) \left(\frac{e_C C_u}{2.5P} \right)^{0.4} \right]^{-9.185} \quad \text{for } 1 \leq \kappa \leq 4$$

For individual bearings, reliability is the probability that the bearing will attain or exceed a specified design life. The modified rating life for reliability L_{nm} and three values of the life modification factor for reliability a_1 are considered:

$a_1 = 1 \rightarrow 90\%$ reliability

$a_1 = 0.64 \rightarrow 95\%$ reliability

$a_1 = 0.25 \rightarrow 99\%$ reliability

These factors are applied in the modified rating life equation:

$$L_{nm} = a_1 a_{ISO} L_{10}$$

where n is subscript for probability of failure, in percentage. In this study, the bearing with 99% reliability was adopted.

3 Reference structure

3.1 Jacket and tower

The stresses that occur during the operation were observed to be higher than of those that occur for the extreme 50-year condition with the parked turbine. Thus, the critical design load case is LC23 and fatigue is shown to drive the sizing of the members.

As a result of the high cyclical overturning moments and forces on the tower top, the legs members are submitted to high cyclical stresses, as shown in Figure 27 for a critical connection. This complicates the initial intention to reduce the cross-section of the leg members with respect to the leg joint chords once this reduction would introduce an additional increase on the stress ranges due to the geometrical change of cross sections. Thus, the leg longer members' cross-section was not reduced with respect to the leg joint chord and the legs' diameter was maintained throughout the legs' height.

Figure 27 – Comparison of a typical hot spot stress cycle for the critical connection at leg bottom and adjacent X-member connection for lc11.

As illustrated in Figure 27, the connections to the X-members are less loaded when compared to the adjacent leg connection. Silva (2023) proposed a jacket structure with constant cross-sections throughout the members, where the X-members represented a significant parcel of the total mass without having their capacity fully utilized. So, a reduction of the X-braces cross-sections with respect to the connected leg joint stubs was done for each bay to achieve a better utilization of these members. Table 10 presents the cross-section reduction for different members with respect to the connected member on the leg joint.

Table 10- Final cross-section reduction parameters

Leg long members	X-braces long members				Mud braces
	bay 1 (bottom)	bay 2	bay3	bay 4 (top)	
1	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5

FLS analysis

The resultant damage utilization ratios along critical hot spots of the legs are shown in Figure 28. It is observed from Table 11 that the relative mass of the X-braces could be significantly reduced with respect to the previous study made by Silva (2023). From Figure 28, it is possible to see that the legs could potentially be further optimized if the cross section along the legs' height would be allowed to be independent, as the final leg diameter was determined by the bottom connection that suffer a larger influence from the foundations' flexibility. Thus, the elements of the jacket legs distant to the bottom connection are shown to be sub-utilized in terms of fatigue damage. Therefore, the assumption that the SCF introduced by a change on the leg cross-section would be non-favourable could still be reviewed in the future.

Figure 28 – Fatigue damage utilization on critical connections.

Table 11 – Jacket Mass

Jacket member	Mass [tonnes]	Relative mass [%]
Leg joints	923.5	34.4
Leg long members	944.8	35.2
X joints	61	2.2
X-braces long members	690	25.7
Mud braces	67	2.5
Jacket total mass	2685	-

Table 12 – Tower Mass

	Mass (tonnes)
Tower	1356

It was observed that the aerodynamic loads components have higher harmonics that can potentially excite the system structural response. Even though the most energy content is at 2P, as the rotor contains 2 blades, the 4P and 6P components are noticeable on the amplitude spectrum of these loads, as illustrated in Figure 29 and Figure 30 for the overturning moment component in the wind direction. As per Table 1, the lc10 and lc11 correspondent to the wind speeds 12m/s and 13m/s, respectively.

The tapered tower design was softened such that the system first natural frequency, 0.65Hz, could be reduced to avoid the vicinity of the 6P excitation of the aerodynamic loads and placed in between the range of the 4P and 6P excitation, as shown in Figure 33. It is observed in Figure 28 that the design of a softer tower to avoid an increased amplification of the dynamic response had the compromise of not fully utilizing the tower cross-sections in terms of fatigue.

Figure 29– Amplitude spectrum of the aerodynamic overturning moment M_z for lc10 ($U = 12\text{m/s}$).

Figure 30 – Amplitude spectrum of the aerodynamic overturning moment M_z for lc11 ($U = 13\text{m/s}$).

Figure 31 shows that there is still a dynamic amplification of the response by comparing the damage per load case for a dynamic simulation and quasi-static simulation. This is a result of the different energy content contained in the higher harmonics on the aerodynamic loads for different winds speeds, as it can be seen in the comparison of Figure 29 and Figure 30 for the load cases representing the wind speeds 12m/s and 13m/s.

Figure 31 – Comparison of fatigue damage utilization ratio on the bottom critical connection for the operational load cases from Table 1.

Figure 32 - Power density spectrum (PSD) of the axial force response from the critical connection at the leg bottom, for lc10 ($U = 12\text{m/s}$).

Figure 33 - Power density spectrum (PSD) of the axial force response from the critical connection at the leg bottom, for lc11 ($U = 13\text{m/s}$).

ULS analysis

The aerodynamic loads provided by Ajay (2022) are mean loads for each azimuthal position of the primary rotor over one rotation. Since no turbulence was considered in the aerodynamic load calculation, there is

still some uncertainty on how the extreme load case 1.1 of DNV-ST-0437, representing the ULS 50 years return period, would be calculated by extrapolating the load peak of the operational cases. Considering barely the load peaks of the most critical load case, lc23, with a tentative load factor of 1.25, the higher stress observed occurred at the mud braces reaching a value of 139.4MPa. This represents an utilization ratio of 65% of the yielding capacity of a 235MPa yield strength steel, considering a material factor of 1.1.

The maximum stresses observed on the tower are shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34 – Tower sections maximum stresses.

Buckling analysis

The global buckling capacity of the members was checked by comparing the maximal axial loading to which the member is submitted to the Euler's critical load of that member. In general, lower utilization ratios were observed, with a maximum utilization of 0.10 observed on a mud brace.

Natural frequency analysis

When considering only the jacket and tower, disregarding the rigid rotor inertia, and only considering the rotor mass applied as a punctual mass on the tower top, the first 10 natural frequencies are described in Table 13.

Table 13 – Eigenfrequencies of jacket and tower

f_1 [Hz]	f_2 [Hz]	f_3 [Hz]	f_4 [Hz]	f_5 [Hz]	f_6 [Hz]	f_7 [Hz]	f_8 [Hz]	f_9 [Hz]	f_{10} [Hz]
1.22	1.22	3.10	3.10	3.75	4.02	4.26	4.26	4.41	4.73

f_1

f_2

f_3

f_4

f_5

f_6

f_7

f_8

f_9

f_{10}

Figure 35 – Jacket and tower only eigenmodes.

Emergency stop analysis

The braking loads during an emergency stop were modelled assuming that the rotor could deaccelerate and completely stop in 8 seconds. During this braking interval, a torque equivalent to the rotational inertia of the primary rotor was applied on the tower top. After that, the structural response decay due to the emergency stop was computed and it was shown that each time the turbine is stopped, an equivalent of circa 18min of additional fatigue damage lifetime is consumed at the critical connection at the jacket leg bottom. Thus, if it is assumed that an emergency braking will occur once a week during the turbine operational lifetime of 20 years, a total of circa 12 days of fatigue lifetime would be consumed.

The conical transitions on the X-braces were observed to be more sensitive to the braking loads, while the accumulated value considering the occurrence of one emergency stop a week would consume almost 5 years of fatigue life. However, even though this connection is more sensitive to the braking loads, it is not a critical connection with respect to the operational loads and has a total fatigue lifetime of 67.6 years. This demonstrates that the braking is not critical for the design, while the operational loads are more harmful to the structure in terms of fatigue, which is considered the design driver.

Table 14 – Fatigue life consumed during turbine emergency stop on critical connections.

Connection [NodeID-BeamID*]	Fatigue life consumed		Connection fatigue lifetime, [years]
	Single braking	Accumulated	
67-19	18 min (0,01 days)	12.12 days (0.03 years)	24.3
147-199	1.88 days	4.97 years	67.6

*Figure 53 and Figure 54 in Appendix C illustrate the reference position of the jacket nodes and beams.

3.2 Foundations

ULS analysis

The pile performance is demonstrated in **Error! Reference source not found**. Taking DLC 1 as an example, Figure 37, Figure 38 and Figure 39 show the time domain response of the lateral displacements on the top end of the pile, among which Figure 37, Figure 38 have the same diameter and different thicknesses, and Figure 37 and Figure 39 have different diameters and the same thickness, where “position X” represents the direction along the wind and “position Y” represents the direction cross the wind.

Figure 36 – Pile capacity design.

Figure 37 – Pile top displacement [m] with the pile L=100m, D=2.3m, t=2cm of leg 1 and DLC1.

Figure 38 – Pile top displacement [m] with the pile L=100m, D=2.3m, t=4cm of leg 1 and DLC1.

Figure 39 – Pile top displacement [m] with the pile L=100m, D=2.4m, t=2cm of leg 1 and DLC1.

Theoretically, the thickness of the pile has direct influence on the pile tip resistance which reflects on the t-z curve, as well as the stiffness of the pile itself. While the pile diameter has influence on the pile tip resistance, axial resistance, lateral resistance of the pile-soil system, as well as the stiffness of the pile itself. Thus, the value of the pile diameter would have a more significant effect on the pile performance. However, to limit the horizontal displacement at the pile head, either increasing the thickness or the diameter can gain a significant effect. As shown in Figure 37, the maximum amplitude of the pile top displacement is more than 0.1 m. After increasing the thickness of the pile from 2 cm to 4 cm, the maximum amplitude of the pile top displacement becomes 0.02 m, as shown in Figure 38. Alternatively, increasing the diameter of the pile from 2.3m to 2.4m, the maximum amplitude of the pile top displacement is reduced to 0.015 m, as shown Figure 39. These two strategies are both effective. From these results, we conclude that the pile top displacement largely depends on the pile stiffness itself rather than the lateral support from the soil.

Displacements and deformations

To test the amplitudes of the displacements and pile capacity along the depth of the piles, a group of pile models of 100 m in length and nine different sections from a sequential combination of three diameters 2.2 m, 2.3 m and 2.4 m, and three thicknesses 2 cm, 3 cm and 4 cm, respectively, were applied in the multibody dynamic analysis. These piles are numerated from pile 1 to pile 9, as shown in Figure 40.

Accordingly, the maximum amplitudes of the horizontal displacements along the embedded depth of the piles are shown in Figure 40(a), which considered the combined effect of the X and Y components. Firstly, the largest amplitudes of the displacement for each pile occurs on the top of the pile and drops very fast with the increase of the embedded depth. For the depth below 15 m, the fluctuation of the horizontal displacements is close to zero. Secondly, in general, the amplitudes are reduced by the increase of the diameter or thickness of the piles; but a nonlinear phenomenon is seen from these simulations, for example, the amplitude curves of pile 8 and pile 9 are very close to each other. From the p-y curve properties it is known that when the horizontal displacements are zero, the lateral reaction force is zero. Thus, it is known that the lateral stability of the foundation is mostly contributed by the upper part of the pile. These group of piles exhibit more elastic deformation rather than rigid rotational behaviour.

The maximum amplitudes of the vertical displacements along the embedded depth of the piles are shown in Figure 40(b), from which the largest amplitude of the displacement also occurs on the top of the piles and drops rapidly with the increase of the embedded depth. For the depth below 60 m, the fluctuation of the vertical displacements is close to zero for all the nine piles. According to the properties of the t-z curve, the axial local displacement of the pile indicates how much load will be carried by the soil in that location. When there is no displacement, there is no reaction from the soil-pile system, so the lower part of the pile did not carry any vertical load, which means the pile capacity is enough with a shorter length than the one assigned by ultimate axial pile capacity design. However, when comparing with the theoretical pile capacity design curves as shown in Figure 36, which shows the pile capacity is enough with an embedded length of 25 m for the pile diameter of 2.3 m, these numerical simulation results are more conservative. The pile final length is reviewed in the fatigue analysis later in this section.

Moreover, it is worth mentioning that because of the effect from static load sources such as gravity and the buoyancy of the wind turbine, there is a squeeze on the pile which makes its real length shorter than the designed length. The values of the accumulative deformation on each section of the pile according to the lower end of the pile due to static pressure are shown in Figure 40(c), where the maximum value is 25 mm and the minimum value is 10 mm of length reduction. The data for Figure 40(b) take this effect into consideration.

Figure 40 - The maximum amplitudes of the horizontal (a) and vertical displacements (b) along the pile, as well as the average values of accumulative vertical deformation (c) according to the lower end of the pile, DLC 1, Leg 1.

FLS analysis

Pile sections for FLS analysis are shown in Figure 41. As the fatigue damage is significantly higher on the top end of the piles than at the lower end, sections samples are checked intensively from the top part of the piles and are checked sparsely from the lower part of the piles. The sections at 0m to -3m from the mudline are checked on each pile (#1 - #13), and sections at -10m, -80m and -130m under the mudline are checked on one pile (#14 - #17). The total length of the piles is 140m, higher than the one estimated by the ultimate axial pile design.

Since the top displacement, stresses and fatigue damage of the piles are significantly higher than the ones on the lower part of the piles, to reduce the cost, piles with transition sections from inside of the cylinder were analysed. The FLS utilization ratio for 8 hot spot points around the pile cross section are shown in Figure 42, where for section 1-14 the outer diameter is 3m and the inner diameter is 2.68 m, and for sections 15-17, the outer diameter is 3m and the inner diameter is 2.90m. The results show that the piles satisfy 200 years design life as non-inspectable structures of the wind turbine. Thus, the transition section of the piles should be applied at around 20m under the mudline.

Figure 41 – Pile sections ID for FLS analysis.

Figure 42 - Pile sections' fatigue utilization ratio at 8 points around the cross- section of sections 1 - 14, the outer diameter is 3m and the inner diameter is 2.68 m, and for section 15 - 17, the outer diameter is 3m and the inner diameter is 2.90m.

3.3 Cross arm

The tapered cross sections of the cross-arm are identified in Figure 43, where the dimensions of the extremities are shown in Table 15.

Figure 43 - Cross arm sections' ID.

Table 15 – Cross arm tapered cross-section

Section ID	Diameter [m]	Thickness [m]
13 (Middle)	6.00	0.085
1 (End)	5.97	0.07

The cross-arm FLS analysis is presented for the cross section represented in Figure 44.

Figure 44 – Cross arm fatigue utilization ratios.

3.4 Shaft

The final dimensions of the shaft are presented in Table 16. It can be seen that the initial shaft outer diameter of 1.6 m, estimated by the ULS design, was updated to 3.0 m after the fatigue assessment. Figure 45 shows the fatigue utilization ratio of its cross-sections. These dimensions result in a final mass of 371 tonnes.

Table 16 – Shaft final dimensions

Section	Outer diameter (m)	Inner diameter (m)	Length (m)
at Bearing 1	3.0	1.4	7.4
at Bearing 2	2.2	1.4	5.0
Transition	-	1.4	1.6

Figure 45 - Fatigue utilization ratio of the shaft cross-sections. Section 8 is the transition section.

Shaft cost evaluation

The cost of the shaft is estimated with a combination of the formulas of “Low-speed shaft mass” and “Low-speed shaft cost” in section 3.4.1.5 of NREL report (Fingersh et al., 2006), multiplied by an inflation factor of 1.53 from year 2006 to 2023, and converted from USD to Euro with the current rate of 0.91:

$$Main\ shaft\ cost = 0.01 \times (shaft\ mass / 0.0142)^{2.887 / 2.88} \times 1.53 \times 0.91 = 361\ 618\ euro$$

This is assumed to be a conservative estimate.

3.5 Bearings

The radial and axial loads of Bearing 1 are shown in the Figure 46. The radial load increases rapidly with the increase of wind speed, while the axial load is relatively stable. In low wind speed region, the axial load is higher than the radial load, and in the high-speed region, the radial load is higher.

Figure 46 - Radial and axial loads of Bearing 1, with the rate of the radial and axial load is on the right axis.

The safety factors of Bearing 1 and Bearing 2 are shown in Figure 47. The dynamic safety factors are shown on the left axis, where the design requirement is satisfied when the value is larger than 1. The static safety factors are shown on the right axis, where the design requirement is satisfied when the value is larger than 3. The horizontal axis is the number of rollers of the bearing. It can be found that the optimal number of rollers of Bearing 1 is 26 units, and the optimal one for Bearing 2 is 25 units, which both correspond to the maximum dynamic safety factors and the static safety factors also reach a stable high level.

Figure 47 also summarizes the bearings' parameters. The parameters are determined as inner diameter, d , is the same as the diameter of the shaft; D is determined according to d and the space in the tower; then, the optimal number of rollers of the bearings are selected. The length L_{we} is evaluated independently, which makes the bearing design according to dynamic safety factors reach 99% reliability.

Figure 47 - Safety factors of Bearing, the static factors and guideline value are on the right axis.

Maximum loads on the bearings

Figure 48 - Maximum loads on Bearings.

The final design parameters of the two bearing are shown in Figure 49 and Figure 50.

Figure 49 - Parameters of Bearing 1 with 99% reliability: outer ring outside diameter ($D = 4.5\text{m}$), inner bore diameter ($d = 3.0\text{m}$), pitch circle diameter ($D_{pw} = 3.75\text{m}$), effective roller length ($L_{we} = 1.65\text{m}$), nominal roller diameter ($D_w = 0.28\text{m}$), nominal contact angle ($\alpha = 5^\circ$), estimated total mass ($m_{B1} = 119\text{ ton}$).

Figure 50 - Parameters of Bearing 2 with 99% reliability: outer ring outside diameter (D = 3.2m), inner bore diameter (d = 2.2m), pitch circle diameter (Dpw = 2.7m), effective roller length (Lwe = 1.21m), nominal roller diameter (Dw = 0.2m), estimated total mass (mB2 = 42 ton).

Bearing cost analysis

The total mass of the bearings is estimated as:

$$m_b = 0.8\rho\pi(D^2 - d^2)B/4$$

where $\rho = 7850 \text{ kg/m}^3$ is the density of the material, and $B = 1.3L_{we}$ is the estimated width of the bearing.

The cost of the bearings is estimated with the formula of 'Total bearing system cost' in section 3.4.1.6 of the NREL report (Fingersh et al. ,2006; Malcolm and Hansen, 2006), and multiplied by an inflation factor of 1.53 and a current rate of 0.91:

$$\text{Bearing cost} = \text{bearing mass} \times 17.6 \times 1.53 \times 0.91$$

The cost of the bearings is listed in Table 17, which is largely dependent on the reliability of the bearings. These are assumed to be conservative estimates.

Table 17 – Bearing cost

Bearing	Reliability	L_{we} [m]	Mass [kg]	Cost [euro]
Bearing 1	90 %	1.01	34798	852703
	95 %	1.14	39473	967245
	99 %	1.65	119023	2916583
Bearing 2	90 %	0.77	26661	653315
	95 %	0.90	31232	765312
	99 %	1.21	41896	1026638

4 Discussions

A reference design for X-Rotor wind turbine's jacket and tower was presented, with a total mass of 2685 tonnes and 1356 tonnes, respectively. The jacket's upper and lower widths were maintained from Amiri (2021) as 20m and 30m, so that the final batter angle could be comparable to regular designs, as e.g. the reference UpWind jacket (Vorpahl, 2013). As a design strategy for the jacket, the number of design parameters were reduced by relating them in terms of the connections' SCFs. Two types of connections were defined: the connection in between joints stubs and their chords, defined by the Efthymiou formulation, and the connections in between joints and the longer members of the legs and braces, made by conical transitions.

In the first case, the geometrical ratios that define the respective SCFs were generally fixed at values known to reduce the SCF, except for β and τ . These values were adopted from The Upwind project to maintain a relative proportional stiffness in between legs and braces, and could be further optimized. The geometrical ratios related to the conical transitions were iteratively obtained for a better utilization of the members.

As the larger cyclical operational loads generate a significant axial cyclical load component on the jacket legs, the legs were set to have a constant cross-section throughout their height, to avoid the introduction of SCFs due to a geometry change. A more detailed design of the pile connection could, however, allow a further reduction of the jacket legs' cross-section, as their final dimension was determined by this section. Meanwhile, the use of joint cans allowed the reduction of the braces' long members. This brought the overall jacket mass down with respect to the previous study presented by Silva (2013).

The presence of higher harmonics on the aerodynamic loads required the design of a softer tower so that the system first natural frequency (0.65Hz) could be placed in between the 4P (0.53Hz) and 6P (0.80Hz) components from the aerodynamic loads, at the cost of the tower cross-sections not being completely utilized in terms of fatigue. However, this increases the overall structural reliability of the design.

The turbine emergency stop was simulated, and the braking loads were shown to not be critical for the structure. As no aerodynamic turbulence was assumed, this was not considered in the ULS analysis. However, it was shown that the maximum stresses observed during the operational life consumed 65% of the yielding utilization ratio for the adopted steel, leaving a margin for extremere loads. Similarly, the global buckling of the members was analysed, and it was observed that the biggest utilization was merely 10% of the member capacity against buckling. Thus, the fatigue limit states considering the normal operational loads are the most critical for the structural design, due to the large load cycles.

The design process of the pile foundation of the X-rotor wind turbine was introduced, which included a ULS and FLS analysis. The ULS analysis consists of pile capacity design considering the axial static load and the pile tip resistance, as well as the pile performance analysis, considering the cyclic loads from both the axial direction and the lateral directions. For the FLS analysis, the location for the pile transition section was evaluated and the fatigue life calculated. The piles final length was defined as 140m.

From the design process the pile capacity standards were satisfied first. And then, in order to keep the amplitude of the pile top displacement within a small enough range, the design parameters of the pile needed to be further enlarged to increase the stiffness. Thus, it is concluded that the operational cyclic loads from the joint effect of wind and wave acting on the X-rotor wind turbine are the most critical for the pile design.

The design of the main shaft and bearings for X-rotor wind turbine was explained. Both ULS and FLS conditions were considered. It is found that the FLS has a major effect for the design parameters, due to high cyclic loads during wind turbine operation.

An effort was made to reduce steel mass consumption of the design. For the shaft design, a tapered shaft with integrated manufacturing strategy was proposed. For the bearings, it was shown that the final mass and cost are significantly influenced by the targeted reliability of the bearings.

It was also found that it is likely that a better shaft design in terms of cost is achieved with larger and thinner shell thickness, but at the same time, the bearings will be larger and cost more. To further reduce the cost of the shaft and bearings, a joint analysis and optimization of the shaft-bearing system might be worthwhile.

5 Conclusions

This study presents a reference design for cross-arm, shaft, bearings, jacket and foundations for the 2-bladed X-Rotor wind turbine. Even though the adoption of 2 blades results, from a support structure point of view, in a non-optimum balance of aerodynamic loads, this study has developed a better understanding of the X-Rotor's support structure configuration and its behaviour. It was observed that the overall mass of the structural components is high, when compared to standard HAWTs of similar power. The fatigue limit state was demonstrated to drive the dimensions of the support structure design, due to the large load cycles generated. The adoption of a 3-bladed X-Rotor turbine is expected to result in a much better balance of aerodynamic loads at the tower top level, which would reduce the load cycles on the substructure significantly. This could lead to a significant reduction of the overall mass of the support structure, as the trend shown in Silva (2013) indicates. In addition, 3-blades would enable reliable aerodynamic braking to be employed rather than mechanical brakes. The authors also would like to recommend the study of floating support structure solutions that could made use of different strategies to reduce the effect of high overturning moments on the structural design.

References

1. Amiri, A. K., Carroll, J. (2021) :X-Rotor, an Innovate Offshore Wind Turbine / Background and Draft Design Configurations
2. API: Planning, Designing, and Constructing Fixed Offshore Platforms - Working Stress Design. API RECOMMENDED PRACTICE 2A-WSD TWENTY-SECOND EDITION, NOVEMBER 2014
3. API: Geotechnical and Foundation Design Considerations. ISO 19901-4:2003 (2014)
4. DNV GL 2016 Support structures for wind turbines DNVGL-ST-0126
5. DNV GL 2016 Loads and site conditions for wind turbines DNVGL-ST-0437
6. DNV GL 2016 Fatigue design of offshore steel structures DNVGL-RP-C203
7. Fingersh, L.J., Mohammed, H., and Laxson, A.: Wind Turbine Design Cost and Scaling Model, <https://doi.org/10.2172/897434>, 2006
8. ISO 76 (2006-05-01): Rolling bearings – Static load ratings, 2006-05-15
9. Vorpahl, F., Popko, W., Kaufer, D. - Description of a basic model of the "UpWind reference jacket" for code comparison in the OC4 project under IEA wind annex 30. Fraunhofer IWES, Bremerhaven und Kassel; 2013.
10. Ajay, A. G., Bensason, D., Ferreira, C. (2022):D2.4 X-Rotor performance and loading evaluation report. Technical report. Delft University of Technology
11. Leithead et al (2019): The X-Rotor offshore wind turbine concept. Journal of Physics: Conference Series 1356:012031.
12. Li, L. Gao, Z., Moan, T.: Joint Distribution of Environmental Condition at Five European Offshore Sites for Design of Combined Wind and Wave Energy Devices. Journal of Offshore Mechanics and Arctic Engineering 137(3) (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4029842>
13. Lotsberg, I.: Stress concentration factors at circumferential welds in tubulars, Marine Structures, 11, 207-230, [https://doi.org/10.16/S0951-8339\(98\)00014-8](https://doi.org/10.16/S0951-8339(98)00014-8),1998.
14. Malcolm, D. J. and Hansen, A. C.: WindPACT Turbine Rotor Design Study: June 2000-June2002 (Revised), <https://doi.org/10.2172/15000964>, 2006
15. Nejad, A.R., Guo, Y., Gao, Z., and Moan, T.: Development of a 5 MW reference gearbox for offshore wind turbines, Wind Energy, 19, 1089-1106, <https://doi.org/10.1003/we.1884>, 2016
16. Oest, J., Sorensen, R., Overgaard, L., Lund, E.: Structural optimization with fatigue and ultimate limit constraints of jacket structures for large offshore wind turbines. Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimization 55(3), 779–793 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00158-016-1527-x>. mangler vol og no/LB
17. Paraschivoiu, I., 2002. Wind turbine design: with emphasis on Darrieus concept, Montréal: Polytechnic International Press.
18. Silva, A.C, Muskulus, M.: Design Basis (2021): D4.1 Establishment of a design basis – X-Rotor. Technical report. Norwegian University of Science and Technology.
19. Schafhirt, S., Zwick, D. and Muskulus, M. (2016) "Two-stage local optimization of lattice type support structures for offshore wind turbines," Ocean engineering, 117, pp. 163–173.

Appendix A – Cross section dimensions

Figure 51 – Jacket cross-section reference ID.

Table 18 Jacket Cross Section dimensions

Cross-section ID	Diameter [m]	Thickness [m]
CS1	2.2	0.14
CS2	2.2	0.14
CS3	1.32	0.08
CS4	1.32	0.08
CS5	0.924	0.08
CS6	0.924	0.08
CS7	2.2	0.14
CS8	2.2	0.14
CS9	1.32	0.08
CS10	1.32	0.08
CS11	0.66	0.04
CS12	0.66	0.04
CS13	2.2	0.14
CS14	2.2	0.14
CS15	1.32	0.08
CS16	1.32	0.08
CS17	0.66	0.04
CS18	0.66	0.04
CS19	2.2	0.14
CS20	2.2	0.14
CS21	1.32	0.08
CS22	1.32	0.08
CS23	0.792	0.05
CS24	0.792	0.04
CS25	2.2	0.14
CS26	1.32	0.08
CS27	0.66	0.04

Figure 52 – Tower cross-section reference.

Table 19 - Tower cross-section dimensions

Cross-section ID	Diameter [m]	Thickness [m]
CS1	10.5	0.12
CS2	9.83	0.11
CS3	9.16	0.10
CS4	8.5	0.10

Appendix B - Nodes and beams reference ID

Figure 53 – Jacket node reference numbering.

Figure 54 – Jacket beam reference numbering.

Appendix C – Jacket nodes' position

Table 20 – Jacket nodes position, X,Y,Z

Node_ID	x	y	z
1	-15.00	-15.00	0.04
2	15.00	-15.00	0.04
3	15.00	15.00	0.04
4	-15.00	15.00	0.04
5	-14.80	-14.80	2.25
6	14.80	-14.80	2.25
7	14.80	14.80	2.25
8	-14.80	14.80	2.25
9	-14.74	-14.74	2.94
10	14.74	-14.74	2.94
11	14.74	14.74	2.94
12	-14.74	14.74	2.94
13	-13.62	-13.62	15.54
14	13.62	-13.62	15.54
15	13.62	13.62	15.54
16	-13.62	13.62	15.54
17	-13.56	-13.56	16.23
18	13.56	-13.56	16.23
19	13.56	13.56	16.23
20	-13.56	13.56	16.23
21	-12.43	-12.43	28.83
22	12.43	-12.43	28.83
23	12.43	12.43	28.83
24	-12.43	12.43	28.83
25	-12.37	-12.37	29.52
26	12.37	-12.37	29.52
27	12.37	12.37	29.52
28	-12.37	12.37	29.52
29	-11.25	-11.25	42.12
30	11.25	-11.25	42.12
31	11.25	11.25	42.12
32	-11.25	11.25	42.12
33	-11.19	-11.19	42.81
34	11.19	-11.19	42.81
35	11.19	11.19	42.81
36	-11.19	11.19	42.81
37	-10.06	-10.06	55.41
38	10.06	-10.06	55.41
39	10.06	10.06	55.41
40	-10.06	10.06	55.41

41	-10.00	-10.00	56.10
42	10.00	-10.00	56.10
43	10.00	10.00	56.10
44	-10.00	10.00	56.10
45	0.00	-14.16	9.49
46	14.16	0.00	9.49
47	0.00	14.16	9.49
48	-14.16	0.00	9.49
49	0.00	-12.97	22.80
50	12.97	0.00	22.80
51	0.00	12.97	22.80
52	-12.97	0.00	22.80
53	0.00	-11.78	36.12
54	11.78	0.00	36.12
55	0.00	11.78	36.12
56	-11.78	0.00	36.12
57	0.00	-10.60	49.44
58	10.60	0.00	49.44
59	0.00	10.60	49.44
60	-10.60	0.00	49.44
61	-14.97	-14.97	0.39
62	14.97	-14.97	0.39
63	14.97	14.97	0.39
64	-14.97	14.97	0.39
65	-14.57	-14.57	4.81
66	14.57	-14.57	4.81
67	14.57	14.57	4.81
68	-14.57	14.57	4.81
69	-13.78	-13.78	13.68
70	13.78	-13.78	13.68
71	13.78	13.78	13.68
72	-13.78	13.78	13.68
73	-13.39	-13.39	18.10
74	13.39	-13.39	18.10
75	13.39	13.39	18.10
76	-13.39	13.39	18.10
77	-12.60	-12.60	26.97
78	12.60	-12.60	26.97
79	12.60	12.60	26.97
80	-12.60	12.60	26.97
81	-12.20	-12.20	31.38
82	12.20	-12.20	31.38
83	12.20	12.20	31.38
84	-12.20	12.20	31.38

85	-11.41	-11.41	40.25
86	11.41	-11.41	40.25
87	11.41	11.41	40.25
88	-11.41	11.41	40.25
89	-11.02	-11.02	44.67
90	11.02	-11.02	44.67
91	11.02	11.02	44.67
92	-11.02	11.02	44.67
93	-10.40	-10.40	51.68
94	10.40	-10.40	51.68
95	10.40	10.40	51.68
96	-10.40	10.40	51.68
97	-13.35	-14.80	2.25
98	13.35	-14.80	2.25
99	14.80	-13.35	2.25
100	14.80	13.35	2.25
101	13.35	14.80	2.25
102	-13.35	14.80	2.25
103	-14.80	13.35	2.25
104	-14.80	-13.35	2.25
105	-13.41	-14.69	3.53
106	13.41	-14.69	3.53
107	14.69	-13.41	3.53
108	14.69	13.41	3.53
109	13.41	14.69	3.53
110	-13.41	14.69	3.53
111	-14.69	13.41	3.53
112	-14.69	-13.41	3.53
113	-12.29	-13.67	14.95
114	12.29	-13.67	14.95
115	13.67	-12.29	14.95
116	13.67	12.29	14.95
117	12.29	13.67	14.95
118	-12.29	13.67	14.95
119	-13.67	12.29	14.95
120	-13.67	-12.29	14.95
121	-12.25	-13.50	16.87
122	12.25	-13.50	16.87
123	13.50	-12.25	16.87
124	13.50	12.25	16.87
125	12.25	13.50	16.87
126	-12.25	13.50	16.87
127	-13.50	12.25	16.87
128	-13.50	-12.25	16.87

129	-11.13	-12.49	28.20
130	11.13	-12.49	28.20
131	12.49	-11.13	28.20
132	12.49	11.13	28.20
133	11.13	12.49	28.20
134	-11.13	12.49	28.20
135	-12.49	11.13	28.20
136	-12.49	-11.13	28.20
137	-11.09	-12.31	30.20
138	11.09	-12.31	30.20
139	12.31	-11.09	30.20
140	12.31	11.09	30.20
141	11.09	12.31	30.20
142	-11.09	12.31	30.20
143	-12.31	11.09	30.20
144	-12.31	-11.09	30.20
145	-9.97	-11.31	41.43
146	9.97	-11.31	41.43
147	11.31	-9.97	41.43
148	11.31	9.97	41.43
149	9.97	11.31	41.43
150	-9.97	11.31	41.43
151	-11.31	9.97	41.43
152	-11.31	-9.97	41.43
153	-9.94	-11.12	43.55
154	9.94	-11.12	43.55
155	11.12	-9.94	43.55
156	11.12	9.94	43.55
157	9.94	11.12	43.55
158	-9.94	11.12	43.55
159	-11.12	9.94	43.55
160	-11.12	-9.94	43.55
161	-8.82	-10.13	54.67
162	8.82	-10.13	54.67
163	10.13	-8.82	54.67
164	10.13	8.82	54.67
165	8.82	10.13	54.67
166	-8.82	10.13	54.67
167	-10.13	8.82	54.67
168	-10.13	-8.82	54.67
169	-8.55	-10.00	56.10
170	8.55	-10.00	56.10
171	10.00	-8.55	56.10
172	10.00	8.55	56.10

173	8.55	10.00	56.10
174	-8.55	10.00	56.10
175	-10.00	8.55	56.10
176	-10.00	-8.55	56.10
177	-0.93	-14.19	9.08
178	0.93	-14.19	9.08
179	14.19	-0.93	9.08
180	14.19	0.93	9.08
181	0.93	14.19	9.08
182	-0.93	14.19	9.08
183	-14.19	0.93	9.08
184	-14.19	-0.93	9.08
185	-0.93	-14.12	9.90
186	0.93	-14.12	9.90
187	14.12	-0.93	9.90
188	14.12	0.93	9.90
189	0.93	14.12	9.90
190	-0.93	14.12	9.90
191	-14.12	0.93	9.90
192	-14.12	-0.93	9.90
193	-0.65	-13.00	22.49
194	0.65	-13.00	22.49
195	13.00	-0.65	22.49
196	13.00	0.65	22.49
197	0.65	13.00	22.49
198	-0.65	13.00	22.49
199	-13.00	0.65	22.49
200	-13.00	-0.65	22.49
201	-0.65	-12.94	23.12
202	0.65	-12.94	23.12
203	12.94	-0.65	23.12
204	12.94	0.65	23.12
205	0.65	12.94	23.12
206	-0.65	12.94	23.12
207	-12.94	0.65	23.12
208	-12.94	-0.65	23.12
209	-0.64	-11.81	35.78
210	0.64	-11.81	35.78
211	11.81	-0.64	35.78
212	11.81	0.64	35.78
213	0.64	11.81	35.78
214	-0.64	11.81	35.78
215	-11.81	0.64	35.78
216	-11.81	-0.64	35.78

217	-0.64	-11.75	36.46
218	0.64	-11.75	36.46
219	11.75	-0.64	36.46
220	11.75	0.64	36.46
221	0.64	11.75	36.46
222	-0.64	11.75	36.46
223	-11.75	0.64	36.46
224	-11.75	-0.64	36.46
225	-0.75	-10.63	49.00
226	0.75	-10.63	49.00
227	10.63	-0.75	49.00
228	10.63	0.75	49.00
229	0.75	10.63	49.00
230	-0.75	10.63	49.00
231	-10.63	0.75	49.00
232	-10.63	-0.75	49.00
233	-0.75	-10.56	49.88
234	0.75	-10.56	49.88
235	10.56	-0.75	49.88
236	10.56	0.75	49.88
237	0.75	10.56	49.88
238	-0.75	10.56	49.88
239	-10.56	0.75	49.88
240	-10.56	-0.75	49.88
241	-15.00	-15.00	0.00
242	15.00	-15.00	0.00
243	15.00	15.00	0.00
244	-15.00	15.00	0.00